

THE EFFECT OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE, ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT, CAREER DEVELOPMENT AND ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION ON EMPLOYEE ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR IN THE TIRE INDUSTRY IN INDONESIA

MOHAMAD ZEIN SALEH, DEDI PURWANA and MOHAMMAD RIZAN

Jakarta State University, Indonesia.

ABSTRACT

This study aims to find the direct effect of Quality of Work Life and Career Development on Organizational Citizenship Behavior and the indirect effect of Quality of Work Life and Career Development on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Organizational Commitment and Entrepreneurial Orientation. This research is explanatory through hypothesis testing to test the nature of the relationship and influence between variables. Statistical analysis used is Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) analysis. The results showed that Quality of Work Life and Career Development had a positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior; Quality of Work Life has a positive effect on Organizational Commitment; Organizational Commitment has a positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior; Career Development has a positive effect on Entrepreneurial Orientation; Entrepreneurial Orientation has a positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior; Quality of Work Life has a positive indirect effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Organizational Commitment; Career Development has a positive indirect effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Entrepreneurial Orientation.

Keywords: Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Quality of Work Life, Career Development, Organizational Commitment, Entrepreneurial Orientation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Productivity and quality of human resources in a company can be influenced by various factors, including Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Organizational Citizenship Behavior can improve the quality of human resources in the company because Organizational Citizenship Behavior is believed to be able to: 1. increase worker productivity, 2. increase manager productivity, 3. save resources owned by management and the organization as a whole, 4. help save energy resources which is rare for maintaining group function, 5. effective means to coordinate work group activities, 6. increase the organization's ability to attract and retain the best employees, 7. increase the stability of organizational performance, and increase the organization's ability to adapt to environmental changes (1). Employees will be willing to give their best performance outside of their official duties because they feel that the organization provides what they expect. Employees who feel that they are supported by the organization will give it back and reduce the imbalance in the relationship by engaging in Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Organizational Citizenship Behavior is also influenced

by the relationship between superiors and subordinates that have been established so far. The more subordinates feel close to their superiors, feel trusted by their superiors and feel cared for by their superiors, the higher their Organizational Citizenship Behavior(2). Thus, the purpose of this research is to investigate the effect of Quality of Work Life, Organizational Commitment, Career Development and Entrepreneurial Orientation on Employee Organizational Citizenship Behavior of the Tire Industry, case in Indonesia.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Citizenship Behavior is believed to be able to increase employee work productivity with indicators:

- a. Altruism is an initiative behavior shown by helping or helping colleagues in the organization voluntarily.
- b. Courtesy is the behavior of individuals who maintain good relations with their co-workers in order to avoid disputes between members in the organization.
- c. Sportsmanship is the individual's willingness to accept whatever is set by the organization even in inappropriate circumstances.
- d. Conscientiousness is a high dedication or dedication to work and the desire to exceed the standard of achievement in every aspect.
- e. Civic Virtue is individual behavior that shows that the individual has a responsibility to be involved, participate, participate, and care in various activities organized by the organization.

Quality of Work Life according to (3) is a process in which organizations respond to employee needs by developing mechanisms to allow employees to give full advice and participate in making decisions and managing their work life in a company. Quality of Work Life is a process by which organizations respond to employee needs by developing mechanisms to allow employees to give full advice and participate in making decisions and managing their work life in a company. Meanwhile, according to (6), Quality of Work Life is very important and is a necessity for the company itself to attract and retain employees to be loyal to the company. So many managers are trying to reduce dissatisfaction with the quality of work life of their employees. Quality of Work Life can be done by providing a sense of security at work, job satisfaction, appreciation at work and creating conditions for growth and development so as to increase the dignity of employees. In addition, to increase the loyalty of workers to serve the company, work happily and safely so that it affects a good work climate which will have an impact on effectiveness and productivity. The Quality of Work Life indicators according to Cascio are as follows:

1. Innovative revenue system

The remuneration given to employees must be able to meet their daily needs and in accordance with the prevailing wage standards in the labor market.

2. Work environment

Availability of a conducive work environment including comfort, security and safety in the workplace

3. Work restructuring

Provide opportunities for employees to get challenging jobs and opportunities to develop themselves

(7) in his research focuses on the relationship between Quality of Work Life and Organizational Citizenship Behavior of employees. Other studies that strengthen the opinion that there is a relationship between Quality of Work Life and Organizational Citizenship Behavior are in the research of Pradhan et al (2016), Dirgahayu (2020), Inceng et al (2019). Their research shows that there is a strong influence of Quality of Wok Life on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. From the opinion above, it is suspected that Quality of Work Life has a direct positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Organizational Commitment in general can be interpreted as an employee's attachment to the company where the employee works. Commitment is needed by the organization so that competent human resources in the organization can be maintained and maintained properly.

(4) suggested Organizational Commitment refers to the emotional attachment of employees, identification with and involvement in certain organizations. Mayer and Allen formulate that employees who have organizational commitment will work with dedication because employees who have high commitment consider that the important thing to be achieved is the achievement of tasks in the organization (5). According to (8), Organizational Commitment is the degree to which employees are involved in their organization and wish to remain members, which contains an attitude of loyalty and willingness of employees to work optimally for the organization where the employee works. With reference to the opinions of Meyer and Allen, Curtis and Wright and S.G.A. Smeenk identified Organizational Commitment in the following indicators (9):

- a. Affective commitment: a person's emotional involvement in the organization in the form of feelings of love for the organization.
- b. Continuance commitment: a person's perception of the costs and risks of leaving the current organization. That is, there are two aspects to continuance commitment, namely: it involves personal sacrifice when leaving the organization and the absence of alternatives available to the person.
- c. Normative commitment: a moral dimension based on a feeling of obligation and responsibility to the employing organization

Research conducted by Devece et al (2016), The and Sun (2012), Afsar et al (2018), Marsidini& Rosalinda (2014). found the effect of Organizational Commitment and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. From the above opinion, it is suspected that Organizational Commitment has a direct positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Career Development according to (10) is a staffing activity that helps employees plan their future careers in the organization, so that the organization and the employees concerned can develop themselves to the maximum. Career Development used by organizations is inseparable from career planning. Every employee in the company before developing his career must have a careful career planning first. Career Development according to (11) is defined as a series of separate work activities and gives a position and meaning in a person's life history. (12) argues that the word career can be viewed from two different perspectives, namely from an objective and a subjective perspective. Viewed from an objective perspective, a career is a sequence of positions occupied by a person during his life, while from a subjective perspective, a career is a change in values, attitudes, and motivations that occur as a person gets older. Both perspectives focus on the individual and assume that each individual has some degree of control over his or her own destiny so that the individual can manipulate opportunities to maximize the success and satisfaction that comes from his or her career. Career Development is a condition that indicates an increase in a person's status in an organization on a career path that has been defined in the organization. Career Development aims to match the needs and goals of employees with the career opportunities available in the organization today and in the future. Therefore, efforts to establish a career development system that is well designed will be able to assist employees in determining their own career needs and adjusting the needs of employees with the needs of the organization. Career Development depends on the career path that has been planned by each company. Career Development indicators are:

- a. Education; is a formal learning process for employees so that they can know, evaluate and apply any knowledge gained from the learning process in the classroom.
- b. Training; is a company activity that is intended to improve and develop the skills and knowledge of employees according to the wishes of the company concerned.
- c. Promotion; is a change position or title from a lower level to a higher level, change this will usually be followed by an increase in responsibilities, rights, and social status somebody.
- d. Mutations, mutations are part of the process of activities that can develop a person's position or status in an organization. A mutation in a narrow sense is a change from a position in one class to a position in another class of the same level in the salary plan. Meanwhile, in a broader sense, mutation is a change in position/position/place/work carried out both horizontally and vertically (promotion/demotion) within an organization.

Research conducted by (13) found the influence of Career Development and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. From the above opinion, it is suspected that Career Development has a direct positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior

In a company, Entrepreneurial Orientation must be present in every employee. This is in accordance with the nature of the company, namely seeking profit. According to (14), Entrepreneur is a person who creates a new business in the face of risk and uncertainty with

the aim of achieving profit and growth by identifying opportunities and gathering the necessary resources to take advantage of these opportunities. Entrepreneurial Orientation is reflected in the behavior of always producing products that are in accordance with the specifications and required by the market so that the product can be accepted by the market. To achieve this, every individual in the company must always have an entrepreneurial orientation. While according to (15), Entrepreneurial Orientation is defined as a description of how new entry is carried out by companies and can increase competitive human resources. Entrepreneurial Orientation emphasizes the spirit of creating business innovation as a refresher from business bottlenecks that often accompany the initial steps of innovation. In essence, entrepreneurship is the nature, characteristics, and character of someone who has the will to bring innovative ideas into the real world creatively. Entrepreneurial Orientation indicators are as follows:

1. Innovativeness

There is a tendency to engage in creativity and experimentation through the process, introduction of new products and their development.

2. Risk tasking

Is the act of exploring the unknown before or allocating significant resources to do something in an uncertain environment.

3. Pro activeness

Is an opportunity seeking, forward-looking perspective characterized by getting to know new products ahead of competitors and acting in anticipation of customer demand.

4. Competitive aggressiveness

Is the intensity of the company's efforts to outperform competitors and is characterized by an offensive attitude or response or aggressive response to competitors' actions.

Research related to Entrepreneurial Orientation includes Martins and Perez (2020), Mohammadi (2021), Mustafa et al (2016), Prince (2012), Breugst et al (2012) and Schmutzler (2019). From the above opinion, it is suspected that Entrepreneurial Orientation has a direct positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

III. METHODOLOGY

The population in this study are employees who work in the production department at 4 (four) tire companies in Indonesia, totaling 11,728. Determination of the unit of analysis using purposive sampling technique, namely the sampling technique based on certain considerations. The criteria used in this study are employees who work in the production department and have been appointed as permanent employees of the company. Determining the number of samples using the Slovin formula, obtained 400 samples that will be used in this study. This study uses a survey method through the distribution of questionnaires

distributed to employees of the production department. The questionnaire contains a number of questions regarding Organizational Citizenship Behavior Quality of Work Life, Organizational Commitment, Career Development and Entrepreneurial Orientation along with explanations so that respondents can fill in clearly and understand the intent and purpose of the questionnaire. The question instrument in this study was made based on the indicators of the previous research variables. Statistical analysis used is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis.

IV. RESULT & DISCUSSION

Validity and Reliability Test

The construct or variable level validity was analyzed using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value. Table 1 shows that all variables have an AVE value > 0.5. Therefore, it can be concluded that all variables are declared valid. The construct or variable reliability test was analyzed based on the Composite Reliability (CR) value. The recommended CR value is >0.7 (16). The test results in Table 1 show that all variables have CR values ranging from 0.893 to 0.941 and more than 0.7. Therefore, it can be concluded that all variables are reliable.

Table-1: Variable Validity & Reliability Test Results

Variable	AVE	CR
Quality of Work Life	0,598	0,930
Career Development	0,606	0,924
Organizational Commitment	0,517	0,893
Entrepreneurial Orientation	0,561	0,933
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0,555	0,941

Descriptive analysis of respondents' answers is used to see the tendency of respondents in answering the statement items of all variables and indicators. Respondents' answers were then analyzed using a category with an interval scale that was calculated from the highest score reduced by the lowest score divided by five, so that an interval of 0.80 was obtained. Based on (17) with an interval of 0.80, the categorization system is shown in Table 2.

Table-2: Categories of Respondents' Answers

No.	Score	Categories
1	1,00-1,80	Very low
2	1,81-2,60	Low
3	2,61-3,40	Fair
4	3,41-4,20	High
5	4,21-5,00	Very high

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) Results

The results of the KMO value and the Barlett test for the Quality of Work Life variable are shown in Table 3. Based on the table, it can be seen that the KMO value for the Quality of Work Life variable is 0.783 greater than 0.5 and the significance of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is $0.000 < 0.05$. This value indicates that the indicators studied have a high and significant correlation and therefore the data can be factored.

Table-3: Results of KMO and Barlett Test Quality of Work Life

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0,783
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2547,999
	df	36
	Sig.	0.000

The results of the KMO and Barlett test scores for the Career Development variable are shown in Table 4. Based on the table, it can be seen that the KMO value for the Career Development variable is 0.685 greater than 0.5 and the significance of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is $0.000 < 0.05$. This value indicates that the indicators studied have a high and significant correlation and therefore the Career Development variable data can be factored.

Table-4: Results of KMO and Barlett Test Career Development

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0,685
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1851,071
	df	28
	Sig.	0,000

The results of the KMO and Barlett test values of the Organizational Commitment variable are shown in Table 5. Based on the table, it can be seen that the KMO value of the Organizational Commitment variable is 0.657 greater than 0.5 and the significance of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is $0.000 < 0.05$. This value indicates that between the indicators studied have a high and significant correlation and therefore the data on the Organizational Commitment variable can be factored.

Table-5: Results of KMO and Barlett Test Organizational Commitment

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0,657
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2288,781
	df	28
	Sig.	0,000

The results of the KMO and Barlett test values for the Entrepreneurial Orientation variable are shown in Table 6. Based on the table, it can be seen that the KMO value for the Entrepreneurial Orientation variable is 0.771 greater than 0.5 and the significance of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is $0.000 < 0.05$. This value indicates that the indicators studied have a high and significant correlation and therefore the Entrepreneurial Orientation variable data can be factored.

Table-6: Results of KMO and Barlett Test Entrepreneurial Orientation

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0,771
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3412,146
	df	55
	Sig.	0,000

The results of the KMO and Barlett test values for the Organizational Citizenship Behavior variable are shown in Table 7. Based on the table, it can be seen that the KMO value for the Organizational Citizenship Behavior variable is 0.788 greater than 0.5 and the significance of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is $0.000 < 0.05$. This value indicates that between the indicators studied have a high and significant correlation and therefore the variable data on Organizational Citizenship Behavior can be factored.

Table-7: Results of KMO and Barlett Test Organizational Citizenship Behavior

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0,788
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx, Chi-Square	4061,755
	df	78
	Sig,	0,000

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Analysis Results
 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Figure 1: Full Model CFA

Table-8: Results of Feasibility Test Full Model CFA

Index	Cut-Off Value	Result	Description
Absolute Measures			
χ^2 (chi-square)		2,686	
Df		1099	
Probability	$\geq 0,05$	0,000	Not Fit
Chi-square/df	≤ 2	2,444	Not Fit
GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,785	Not Fit
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,060	Fit
Incremental Fit Measures			
NFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,828	Not Fit
CFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,890	Not Fit
TLI	$\geq 0,95$	0,882	Not Fit
Parsimony Fit Measures			
AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,760	Not Fit
PGFI	$\geq 0,60$	0,704	Fit

The results of the CFA fit model test are shown in Figure 2 and Table 9 below:

Figure 2: Fit Model CFA

Table-9: Results of the CFA Model Fit Feasibility Test

Index	Cut-Off Value	Result	Description
Absolute Measures			
χ^2 (chi-square)		793,371	
Df		564	
Probability	$\geq 0,05$	0,000	Not Fit
Chi-square/df	≤ 2	1,407	Fit
GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,901	Fit
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,032	Fit
Incremental Fit Measures			
NFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,903	Fit
CFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,969	Fit
TLI	$\geq 0,95$	0,966	Fit
Parsimony Fit Measures			
AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,883	Not Fit
PGFI	$\geq 0,60$	0,763	Fit

Based on Table 9, it can be seen that the results of further testing of the CFA model have a better feasibility index. Chi-square probability of $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that the index does not fit and the model does not fit the data. However, the Chi-square test is very sensitive to sample size, the larger the sample size, the more likely the Chi-square test will be significant (17). Therefore, researchers can assess the feasibility of the model by using other feasibility indices.

The GFI value of $0.901 \geq 0.90$ and the RMSEA of $0.032 \leq 0.08$ indicate that the model has fulfilled good absolute fit indices. Then in terms of incremental fit measurement, all indices have exceeded the cut-off value set, namely NFI of $0.903 \geq 0.90$, CFI of $0.969 \geq 0.90$, and TLI of $0.966 \geq 0.95$. Furthermore, the AGFI value of 0.883 is still less than the specified cut-off value of 0.90 so that the AGFI index is considered unfit. Although the AGFI index is not fit, the PGFI index of 0.763 is greater than the cut-off value of 0.60 and thus still represents a good measure of parsimony fit. According to (18), using 4-5 GOF criteria representing absolute fit indices, incremental fit indices, and parsimony fit indices are considered adequate to assess the feasibility of a model. Therefore, it can be concluded that the CFA model is fit or meets the criteria for Goodness of Fit Indices (GOF).

Furthermore, the validity of each construct is evaluated by looking at the components of convergent validity and discriminant validity. Convergent validity requires that each indicator of a particular construct must converge or share a high proportion of variance (18). Convergent validity can be accessed from the magnitude of the factor loading of each item or indicator, the average variance extracted (AVE), and reliability with construct reliability (CR) measurements.

The results of the convergent validity test are shown in Table 10. These results indicate that all items have a factor loading value of more than 0.5, indicating good item validity. Then, all constructs/variables have an AVE value > 0.5 and a CR value > 0.7 . Thus, all constructs have met the criteria of good convergent validity.

Table-10: Convergent Validity Test Results for CFA Constructs

Construct	Item	Factor Loading	AVE	CR
Quality of Work Life	QWL1	0,748	0,68	0,927
	QWL2	0,997		
	QWL5	0,61		
	QWL7	0,767		
	QWL9	0,982		
	QWL10	0,789		
Career Development	CD2	0,996	0,902	0,62
	CD3	0,64		
	CD4	0,554		
	CD6	0,997		
	CD7	0,818		
	CD9	0,583		
Organizational Commitment	OC1	0,85	0,964	0,80
	OC2	0,998		
	OC5	0,997		
	OC6	0,879		
	OC7	0,998		
	OC9	0,667		
Entrepreneurial Orientation	EO1	0,857	0,958	0,70
	EO3	0,92		
	EO4	0,805		
	EO5	0,85		
	EO7	0,93		
	EO8	0,663		
	EO10	0,836		
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	OCB1	0,93	0,972	0,80
	OCB3	0,96		
	OCB5	0,931		
	OCB6	0,989		
	OCB8	0,807		
	OCB9	0,934		
	OCB11	0,609		
	OCB12	0,932		
	OCB13	0,765		
	OCB15	0,909		

Then discriminant validity is a measurement of the extent to which a construct is completely different from other constructs. The results of the discriminant validity test in Table 11 show that each construct has good discriminant validity. This can be seen from the value of the square root of the AVE for each construct which is higher than the correlation value between constructs.

Table-11: Discriminant Validity Test Results

Variable	QWL	CD	OC	EO	OCB
QWL	0,827				
CD	0,152	0,787			
OC	0,403	0,228	0,906		
EO	0,152	0,225	0,189	0,862	
OCB	0,355	0,295	0,404	0,235	0,884

Structural Model

The results of the feasibility test of the structural model in Table 12 show that the value of the feasibility of the structural model is not much different from the results of the feasibility of the CFA fit model. The structural model has met the model fit criteria as indicated by the Chi-square/df value of $1.431 \leq 2$, GFI $0.90 \geq 0,900.90$, and RMSEA $0.033 \leq 0,080.08$ for the measurement of absolute fit indices. Then the NFI value is $0.902 \geq 0,900.90$, CFI is $0.968 \geq 0,900.90$, and TLI is $0.965 \geq 0,900.95$ which represents incremental fit indices. Then the parsimony fit indiceis fit as seen from the PGFI value of $0.766 \geq 0.60$.

Table-12: Structural Model Feasibility Test Results

Index	Cut-Off Value	Result	Description
Absolute Measures			
χ^2 (chi-square)		811,532	
Df		567	
Probability	$\geq 0,05$	0,000	Not Fit
Chi-square/df	≤ 2	1,431	Fit
GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,900	Fit
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,033	Fit
Incremental Fit Measures			
NFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,902	Fit
CFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,968	Fit
TLI	$\geq 0,95$	0,965	Fit
Parsimony Fit Measures			
AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,882	Not Fit
PGFI	$\geq 0,60$	0,766	Fit

Figure 3: Structural Model

Hypothesis Test Results

Table 13. summarizes the results of the standard parameter estimates for the six direct effect hypotheses. The decision to assess whether the hypothesis is supported or not is based on the results of the C.R and p-values. The direct influence hypothesis is said to be significant if it has a C.R value > 1.96 and a p-value < 0.05.

Table-13: Results of Direct Effect Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Direct Effect	C.R	P-Value	Description
H1 Quality of Work Life → Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0,201	2,364	0,018	Supported
H2 Career Development → Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0,208	2,736	0,006	Supported
H3 Quality of Work Life → Organizational Commitment	0,418	3,158	0,002	Supported
H4 Organizational Commitment → Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0,278	2,182	0,029	Supported
H5 Career Development → Entrepreneurial Orientation	0,267	3,587	0,000	Supported
H6 Entrepreneurial Orientation → Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0,144	2,077	0,038	Supported

To test the effect of the mediation hypothesis, this study uses the bootstrapping method on SEM AMOS which can be seen in Table 14 as follow as:

Table-14: Mediation Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis		Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Confidence Interval		P-Value	Description
				Low	High		
H7	QWL → OC → OCB	(0,418) (0,278)	0,116	0,025	0,133	0,006	Supported
H8	CD → EO → OCB	(0,267) (0,144)	0,038	0,011	0,155	0,034	Supported

The results of testing the mediation hypothesis using the bootstrap method in Table 14 show that both mediation hypotheses are supported. The hypothesis regarding the indirect effect of Quality of Work Life (QWL) on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) through Organizational Commitment (OC), has an indirect effect of 0.116 and a confidence interval ranging from 0.025-0.133 greater than 0. Then the p-value of 0.006 <0.05, which means the effect is significant. Therefore, this study supports the hypothesis which states that Quality of Work Life (QWL) has a positive indirect effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) through Organizational Commitment (OC).

Furthermore, the hypothesis regarding the indirect effect of Career Development (CD) on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) through Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO), has an indirect effect of 0.038 and a confidence interval that ranges from 0.011-0.155 greater than 0. Then the p-value of 0.034 <0.05, which means the effect is significant. Therefore, this study supports the hypothesis which states that Career Development (CD) has a positive indirect effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) through Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO).

Based on the results of the analysis of respondents' answers, the researchers found several things related to Quality of Work Life that need to be evaluated and improved so that the influence of Quality of Work Life on Organizational Commitment and Organizational Citizenship Behavior is greater. Overall, respondents felt that the company had provided enough of the Quality of Work Life they expected, but the innovative reward system could still be improved. Leaders can improve an innovative reward system by measuring the achievement of performance, work experience, and the level of difficulty of work received by employees.

Based on the analysis of respondents' answers, the researcher found several things related to Career Development that need to be evaluated and improved so that the influence of Career Development on Entrepreneurial Orientation and Organizational Citizenship Behavior is greater. Overall, respondents feel that the company has provided quite good Career Development. However, the mutation policy still needs to be evaluated and improved because

it has the lowest average value compared to other indicators. Leaders and management must be fairer in transferring employees to other sections or divisions. In addition, employee transfers must also be carried out objectively and through established procedures.

Based on the results of the analysis of respondents' answers, the researchers found several things related to Organizational Commitment that need to be evaluated and improved so that the influence of Organizational Commitment on Organizational Citizenship Behavior is greater. Overall, employees perceive that they have high organizational commitment. Even though employees feel they have a high Affective Commitment, Continuance Commitment, and Normative Commitment to the company, there are still doubts from employees about the commitment they give to the company. This is based on the analysis of respondents' answers which show that some statements have a low average value which indicates that employee organizational commitment still needs to be improved

Leaders of tire industry companies need to evaluate and improve their employees' organizational commitment to the company so that they have a good emotional attachment. Leaders can increase Affective Commitment by inviting their employees to carry out every activity so that employees feel part of the company. In Continuance Commitment, the company can provide rewards that are in accordance with the performance given by employees to their employees, so that employees feel that this company is the best choice in terms of income.

Based on the results of the analysis of respondents' answers, the researchers found several things related to Entrepreneurial Orientation that need to be evaluated and improved so that the influence of Entrepreneurial Orientation on Organizational Citizenship Behavior is even greater. Overall, employees rate that they have a high Entrepreneurial Orientation. However, there are some attitudes that get low scores so that it needs to be paid attention to by the leadership and management of the national tire industry. Employees already have good activity, but are still lacking in terms of innovation. This is based on the analysis of answers from respondents which shows that employees still do not have enough ideas and do work according to the standards that have been set. Therefore, leaders and management in the national tire industry need to improve employee innovativeness, such as implementing participatory leadership. Leaders can provide opportunities for employees to provide new ideas that will increase production effectiveness. In addition, in the decision-making process related to existing problems, the leadership can ask for input from employees. By providing opportunities for employees to provide ideas and opinions, it will train employees to think and be creative so that employees become more innovative.

IV. CONCLUSION

Quality of Work Life and Career Development have a positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior; Quality of Work Life has a positive effect on Organizational Commitment; Organizational Commitment has a positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior; Career Development has a positive effect on Entrepreneurial Orientation; Entrepreneurial Orientation has a positive effect on Organizational Citizenship

Behavior; Quality of Work Life has a positive indirect effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Organizational Commitment; Career Development has a positive indirect effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Entrepreneurial Orientation.

REFERENCES

1. Tefera, C. A and Hunsaker, W. D. (2020). Intangible assets and organizational citizenship behavior: A conceptual model. *Heliyon*, 6(7), e04497.
2. Haryati, E., Mariatin, E and Supriyantini, S. (2014). Pengaruh Persepsi Kepemimpinan Transformasional Dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *Analitika: Jurnal Magister Psikologi UMA*, 6(2), 105-113.
3. Robbins and Timothy, A. (2013). *Organizational Behavior*. Pearson Education Inc.
4. Shane, M., Steven, L and Mary, A.V.G.(2003). *Organizational Behavior* , Second edition. New York: Mc Graw- Hill.
5. Hayati, I. K. (2013). Analisis penerapan Quality of Work Life (QWL) terhadap Kepuasan Kerja dan Komitmen Karyawan Semnas Fekon: Optimisme Ekonomi Indonesia. Antara Peluang dan Tantangan Akademi Telekomunikasi Bogor.
6. Wang, Q. Q., Lv, W. J., Qian, R. L and Zhang, Y. H. (2019). Job burnout and quality of working life among Chinese nurses: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of nursing management*, 27(8), 1835-1844.
7. Farooq, N., Waseem, M., Hussain, B., Iqbal, N., Nawaz, A and Khan, A. (2021). Impact of Knowledge Sharing Culture on Organizational Citizenship Behavior Mediating Role of Organizational Commitment. *Elementary Education Online*, 20(5), 4584-4584.
8. Agustina, T. S., & Ismiati, Y. (2020). The Job Satisfaction of Non-Civil Servant Nurses in Indonesia Public Hospitals. *Jurnal Medicoeticolegal dan Manajemen Rumah Sakit (JMMRS)*, 9(3), 223-236.
9. Smeenk, S. G., Eisinga, R. N., Teelken, J. C., & Doorewaard, J. A. C. M. (2006). The effects of HRM practices and antecedents on organizational commitment among university employees. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 17(12), 2035-2054.
10. Leuhery, F. (2018). Pengaruh Kualitas Sumber Daya Manusia, Disiplin Kerja, Dan Pengembangan Karir Terhadap Prestasi Kerja Pegawai Dinas Perhubungan Provinsi Maluku. *Soso-Q: Jurnal Manajemen*, 6(1), 118-133.
11. Mehrabad, M. S., & Brojeny, M. F. (2007). The development of an expert system for effective selection and appointment of the jobs applicants in human resource management. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 53(2), 306-312.
12. Putra, S. A. (2021). Effect Of Placement And Work Environment On Work Discipline And Their Impact On Performance Of Employee Office Jati Karya Village, Binjai City. *Jurnal Ekonomi LLDIKTI Wilayah 1 (JUKET)*, 1(1), 1-4.
13. Hamzah, H., Hubeis, M., & Hendri, I. (2020). The Effect of Career Development, Justice Organization and Quality of Work Life to Organizational Commitment and Implications to Organizational Citizenship Behavior of Employees at PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIII. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 10(3), 101.
14. Ariyanti, M. (2015). *Kajian Suksepsi Perusahaan Keluarga Pada Perusahaan Garmen Di Bandung (Studi Kasus pada CV Ravina)* (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Komputer Indonesia).

15. Rezazadeh, A., & Mahjoub, M. (2016). Alliance entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial orientation: The mediating effect of knowledge transfer. *Gadjah Mada International Journal of Business*, 18(3), 263-284.
16. Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2011). PLS-SEM: Indeed a silver bullet. *Journal of Marketing theory and Practice*, 19(2), 139-152.
17. Sugiyono, D. (2013). Metode penelitian pendidikan pendekatan kuantitatif, kualitatif dan R&D.
18. Hair Jr, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., & Kuppelwieser, V. G. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM): An emerging tool in business research. *European business review*.